

1 **Early activation of Tlr4 by HBV.**

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6 Activation of TLR4 sensor activity by viral infection is not well understood. We demonstrate here using a
7 primary hepatocyte culture system and RNA-sequencing through measurement of total transcription
8 during HBV infection induction of the lipopolysaccharide sensor *Tlr4* during hepatitis B infection.

9 Citations

10 1. Lee, S.M., Kok, K.H., Jaime, M., Cheung, T.K., Yip, T.F., Lai, J.C., Guan, Y., Webster, R.G., Jin,
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12 influenza virus infection. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 111(10), pp.3793-3798.

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